

An overview of number theory research unit variant development security

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ABSTRACT

Number theory research unit (NTRU) become the most important of security in recent, with its modification of their variant, this paper search of the literature and A number of studies have examined the in public key variant development and security. In general, prior work is limited to a subset of public key increasing complexity but the benefits of speed up encryption/decryption have not been fully established. So this paper will be the basis for those who want to develop and find proposed solutions for new studies of the NTRU algorithm. This paper aims to develop a framework to investigate the NTRU development, had been discovered that despite its development over the years and even its acceptance in round three of post quantum cryptograph, then found that limit study in the new scope of quantum facility and the ability of hybrid of new study.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Cryptography is a technique developed in data security to ensure that the original message is not accessed by an unauthorized person or entity [1]. Hoffstein and colleagues created the Number theory research unit (NTRU) cryptosystem in 1996, they looked for an efficient public-key cryptosystem that is based on restricted polynomials over polynomial rings [2], NTRU's computational complexity is $O(N^2)$ [2]. The hard problems make the security of NTRU strong and resistant to both classical and quantum attacks. NTRU is most important post-quantum cryptosystems. The security of NTRU is linked to a very difficult problem in lattice reduction called the shortest vector problem (SVP) [3], and it is thought that there is no polynomial-time algorithm to solve this problem. The main theory used to build the NTRU cryptosystem, talk about its classical security as well as its resistance to quantum attacks [4]-[6].

In the NTRU cryptosystem, the key generation is more than 200 times faster than in the Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) cryptosystem, and the encryption is almost 3 times faster. The decryption is about 30 times faster [7] Preliminary results was showed on the working [8]. Some variants of NTRU, like Construction Throy Research Unit (CTRU), Quaternionic Theory Research Unit (QTRU), Matrix Formulation (MaTRU), Eisenstein Throy Research Unit (ETRU), a noncommutative analogue of NTRU (NNRU), Ideal lattices Throy Research Unit (ILTRU), and others are called NTRU variants [2]. The NTRU cryptosystem is more efficient and may be able to withstand quantum computers in the long run. It's because the encryption (or signature) and decryption (or varication) speeds are very fast and only use a small amount of space [6]. NTRU is based on reducing the number of lattices. The main attacks on NTRU primitives haven't focused on the hard lattice problems for the last 20 years or so. They have instead focused on other

things [8]. Shor's Algorithm broke RSA and Elliptic-curve cryptography (ECC) in 1994 [9], which is why lattice-based cryptography is so important now. Good understanding of the hard problem Hardware-friendly, fast, and able to run in groups [10]. It will be about 15 years before the quantum computer is ready to be used [11], Forecasting and improving lattice reduction algorithms is still an active research subject after almost 40 years [12].

So in this paper, will review the NTRU algorithms, most of the improvements that worked on over the previous work, review and analyze them, and why they choose for the third round of post-quantum cryptography of National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) candidates, also this paper comparative between NTRU variant especially in public key with efficacy and their security, our contribution proposed to find by Searching most of previous studies and trying to answer the question: is quantum mechanics use to generate the public key of NTRU algorithm in those studies as a parameter or totally generation with eliminate the inverse polynomial?.

2. RESEARCH METHOD OF NTRU

The number theory research unit (NTRU) is a collection of mathematical algorithms for manipulating lists of very small integers and polynomials [9]. NTRU operations are based on objects in the $R = \frac{\mathbb{Z}[X]}{X^N-1}$ truncated polynomial ring As a consequence [12], NTRU may achieve high speeds while using little computing resources [13]. The NTRU key generation technique requires computing the modular multiplicative inverse of F modulo p and q [14], making it the first secure public-key cryptosystem that does not depend on factorization or discrete logarithm concerns [15]. Let f, g polynomial of the form:

$$f = a_0 + a_1X + a_2X^2 + a_3X^3 + \dots + a_{n-1}X^{n-1} + a_nX^n \tag{1}$$

$$g = a_0 + a_1X + a_2X^2 + a_3X^3 + \dots + a_{n-1}X^{n-1} + a_nX^n \tag{2}$$

and NTRU [16] parameter is shown in detail in Table 1.

Parameter of NTRU	Detail
N	Each truncated polynomial has degree N.
P	Small modulo
q	Large modulo
r	Random polynomial
m	Message

2.1. NTRU Key generation

To make public and private keys, first need to find the multiplicative inverse of $f \pmod p$ and $g \pmod q$ so that the public and private keys match [13], [17]. A polynomial multiplicative inverse is not always easy to find. In this case, the extended euclidean algorithm is used to find the greatest common divisor (GCD), and then a series of polynomial factorizations are used [13].

$$F_p * F \equiv 1 \pmod{p} \quad G_p * G \equiv 1 \pmod{p} \tag{3}$$

$$F_q * F \equiv 1 \pmod{q} \quad G_q * G \equiv 1 \pmod{q} \tag{4}$$

Public key[16] H is obtained by using the inverses of the F and G matrices to $\pmod q$ and a random polynomial.

$$h = F_q * g \pmod q \tag{5}$$

2.2. Encryption of NTRU

Sender can transmit an encrypted message to receiver using the NTRU equation and a public key [18]:

$$e = rh + m \pmod q \tag{6}$$

Receiver encrypted message now. Receiver may now transmit e to sender as (6).

2.3. Decryption of NTRU

Receiver wants to decrypt sender message that is received. Then trying to computes the polynomial, it defined by the (7) [18]-[20]:

$$a = f_e \pmod{q} \quad (7)$$

then computes the polynomial b defined by the expression as (8).

$$\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{a} \pmod{\mathbf{p}} \quad (8)$$

Finally, receiver computes the polynomial C defined by the expression as (9).

$$\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{f}_p \mathbf{b} \pmod{p} \quad (9)$$

The original message m will be represented by this polynomial C.

3. SUMMARIZE DEVELOPMENT NTRU

Many non-invertible polynomial NTRU variants exist [21], including CTRU, MaTRU, matrix formulation, QTRU, NNRU, ETRU, ILTRU, and others in Table 2 with detail. while some variations suggest using polynomial rings with coefficients in other rings or another formula [22]. The work was carried out in two phases. The first phase was to prepare an integrated table key generation, encryption, and decryption in Table 2. As for the second phase, these improvements were summarized in detail, and work on analyzing each of these parts to make this paper the basis for those who want to delve into this wide field in Table 3.

Table 2. The efficient and provably secure cryptosystem

N0.	Algorithm	key Generation	Encryption	Decryption
1	NTRU [3]	1 \dot{C}	1 \dot{C} and 1 \dot{A}	2 \dot{C} and 1 \dot{A}
2	BITRU [3], [23]	8 \dot{C}	8 \dot{C} and 1 \dot{A}	16 \dot{C} and 1 \dot{A}
3	BOTRU [24]	8 \dot{C}	8 \dot{C} and 4 \dot{A}	24 \dot{C} and 4 \dot{A}
4	BCTRU [25]	16 \dot{C}	16 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}	32 \dot{C} and 12 \dot{A}
5	QTRU [11], [26]	16 \dot{C}	16 \dot{C} and 4 \dot{A}	32 \dot{C} and 4 \dot{A}
6	PQTRU [3]	32 \dot{C}	32 \dot{C} and 4 \dot{A}	64 \dot{C} and 4 \dot{A}
7	NTRS [27]	36 \dot{C}	18 \dot{C} and 6 \dot{A}	45 \dot{C} and 6 \dot{A}
8	NTRSH [28]	54 \dot{C}	18 \dot{C} and 6 \dot{A}	189 \dot{C} and 6 \dot{A}
9	OTRU [23]	64 \dot{C}	64 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}	1024 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}
10	NTRTE [11]	64 \dot{C}	6 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}	96 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}
11	QOBTRU [23]	64 \dot{C}	64 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}	256 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}
12	QMNTR [29]	80 \dot{C}	80 \dot{C} and 4 \dot{A}	1088 \dot{C} and 4 \dot{A}
13	QOTRU [30]	80 \dot{C}	32 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}	38 \dot{C} and 8 \dot{A}
14	TOTRU [31]	128 \dot{C}	128 \dot{C} and 16 \dot{A}	1536 \dot{C} and 16 \dot{A}
15	HXDTRU [3], [32]	256 \dot{C}	256 \dot{C} and 16 \dot{A}	4096 \dot{C} and 16 \dot{A}

Table 2 shows \dot{C} it is the mean convolution multiplication, and \dot{A} it is the mean polynomial addition the addressed algorithms in Table 2 displayed the ratio of convolution in key generation and encryption/decryption arranged from low to high security with better efficiency. The increased value of convolution made the algorithm more efficient but with the lowest speed encryption-decryption process.

3.1. NTRU variant

Table 3 in APPENDIX shows the surmise of previous research in the same algorithm. But different in public key or finite field based on year. There is an increment in research done in the NTRU algorithm as shown below.

3.2. Discussion

Overall the summary show a high level of agreement in the majority of cases of the mechanism of encryption/decryption of the NTRU expect their key generation is change of the most previous studies as Table 3 shows as many study had been checked in literature finding more information on topic of NTRU public key generation where it was found some of NTRU public key development dependent on multi-

dimensional others depended on replacing the original ring in NTRU like quaternion algebra or Eisenstein, integer algebra and others mathematic algebra. The public key system has been modified and made more secure as a result of this change. In this case, an analytical solution cannot be easily obtained when comparison between the complexity as increasing but lowest speed of encryption and decryption, in this case lead as to ask question how to balance between the complexity of public key and speed of encryption/decryption, this question lead as to think a new method of public key generation is presented and compared with classical way and try to think is quantum is efficient to solve this problem Research in these areas requires studies of topic quantum area. And if the properties of quantum mechanics are used, the degree of complexity can be \sqrt{N} , and it is better from the original case is N^2 . These findings could also be applicable in cases of better speed up the time execution. While maintaining or even increasing the complexity of the data. The result of the study now provides evidence to it is still open way further thinking about the mechanism of evolution, although NTRU was chosen on third round of post quantum cryptography and also it resistance to Shor’s algorithm.

4. CONCLUSION

NTRU was discovered to have an edge over the method in terms of arithmetic operations since it is both quick and requires less storage space. As a result, NTRU has become an extremely ideal alternative for a wide range of applications. as this paper has been presented the most of the wide NTRU development variants, collected these studies and summarized them to be a basic base for those who want to research About the mechanism and how to develop this algorithm, and this is very important for future works, especially NTRU since it was chosen from NIST in round 3 of post-quantum cryptography. Also, this paper, has founded that quantum mechanics has never been used in generating the public key, as a parameter or totally generation with eliminate the inverse polynomial, so this is the answer of the question has been asked at the beginning this paper.

APPENDIX

Table 3. NTRU Previous work with variant and our analysis

N0. Ref	Algorithm	Principle	Finite field /deg	Public key	Attacks	Analysis
[33], [34]	NTRU Non-invertible	It is possible to use NTRU with non-invertible polynomials to extend the capabilities of NTRU Encrypt to include non-invertible polynomials as a means of overcoming the difficulty in locating an invertible polynomial using NTRU Encrypt.	$R_p = \frac{Z_p[x]}{(x^N - 1)}$ $R_q = \frac{Z_q[x]}{(x^N - 1)}$	$h = F_q * g \text{ mod } q$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attack on private key Brute force attack Meet in the middle attack Lattice attack 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> it speedup than original NTRU This extension avoids the challenge of finding “enough” invertible polynomials.
[8], [25], [35], [36]	C_TRU	CTRU develops NTRU encrypt over a binary finite field F2 that is safe against Popov normal form attacks but is entirely vulnerable to linear algebra-based attacks. As a result, CTRU has a non-commutative, secure variation known as NETRU.	$\frac{f_2[T][X]}{X^N - 1}$	$H = g / f \text{ (mod } Q)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private Attack on the key, Meet in the middle attack, Multiple transmission attack Attack on public key using Popov normal form 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CTRU is completely insecure to meet the security criterion for valid decryption CTRU neither improves Performance protects linear algebra attacks
[16], [37]	Ma_TRU	MaTRU uses the linear transformation of two-sided matrix multiplication to work on the ring of k by k matrices of a polynomial in R. MaTRU uses the same number of bits per message as NTRU Encrypt when $nk_2 = N$	$\frac{M_k(L)[X]}{X^{11} - I_{k \times k}}$	$h = F_q * W * G_q \text{ mod } q$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brute force attack Lattice attack 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MaTRU's mproved linear transformation efficiency results in significant speed increases of a factor of O(k) over NTRU.

Table 3. NTRU Previous work with variant and our analysis (*continue*)

N0. Ref	Algorithm	Principle	Finite field /deg	Public key	Attacks	Analysis
[2], [38]	GN_TRU	NTRU Encrypt over the ring of Gaussian integers $\mathbb{Z}[i] = \{a + ib: a, b \in \mathbb{Z}, i^2 = -1\}$ Is proposed by GNTRU. GNTRU is significantly more resistant to lattice attacks than NTRU Encrypt but is not as efficient.	$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[i][X]}{X^N - 1}$	$h = f_q * g \text{ mod } q$	Brute force attack	That the security of NTRU, ETRU, and GNTRU in terms of decryption failure is very similar.
[14], [39], [40]	Matrix_NTRU	Matrix NTRU is the matrix formulation of NTRU Encrypt. This is because the matrix formulation form is more secure when the matrix is invertible or when the matrix has a determinant. Additionally, it may verify that encryption and decryption operate properly without requiring the parameters p and q to be fixed.	$\frac{M(\mathbb{Z})[X]}{X^n - I}$	$H = p * Xq * Y \text{ (modulo } q)$	A matrix is only invertible when it is determinant is discovered	has the capability of transmitting massive amounts of data in the form of matrices, but drawback of If one of the matrix positions is identified
[41]	GB_NTRU	GB-NTRR generalizes NTRU Encrypt to a multivariate polynomial, which in its system is a bivariate polynomial. GB-NTRU may be extended to a twisted group ring variation of NTRU, which contains NTRU defined by x N + 1 and QTRU. It is a critical future task to explore the security of variation of NTRU in the broad framework	$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[X, Y]}{(X^N - 1, Y^N - 1)}$	$h = p \cdot g / f + \alpha$	Lattice attack Brute force attack	It may allow for the selection of smaller f and g allowing for the selection of larger r and m.
[2], [42], [43]	NNRU	NNRU operates on the ring of k by k polynomial matrices in R. In comparison to NTRU Encrypt, NNRU is considered to be more secure against lattice-based attacks. By setting N equal to n(k2), NTRU Encrypt and NNRU have the same plaintext block size.	$\frac{M_k(\mathbb{Z})[X]}{X^n - I_{k \times k}}$	$h \equiv wG_q \text{ (mod } q)$ $H \equiv F_q c \text{ (mod } q)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute force attack, • Meet in the middle attack, • Multiple transmission attacks. 	NNRU is fully safe against lattice attacks and has a large speed boost.
[38]	G_TRU	NTRU Encrypt is generalized over a larger algebra than the Dedekind domain, D. GTRU's underlying algebra can be non-commutative (quaternion algebra or four-dimensional algebra) or even non-associative (octonion algebra or algebra of dimension eight).	$\frac{\mathcal{D}[X]}{X^N - 1}$	$\mathfrak{h} = \bar{\pi}_q(f_q \circ g)$	Lattice attack	The suggested GTRU for IoT is more secure than NTRU. As a result, the GTRU for IoT
[2], [24], [23]	O_TRU	The octonion variant of NTRU Encrypt is proposed by OTRU. OTRU's operation is based on a non-associative octonion algebra, $\mathbb{A} := \{a_0(x) + \sum_{i=1}^7 a_i(x)e_i \mid a_0(x), \dots, a_7(x) \in R\}$ where $R = \mathbb{Z}[X]/(X^N - 1)$ OTRU is faster than NTRU Encrypt	$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[X]}{X^N - 1}$ Octonion algebra (non-associative algebra)	$H = F_q^{-1} \circ G \in A_q$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute force attack, • Meet in the middle attack, • Multiple transmission attack, • Message expansion 	OTRU design and execution will be simple, quick dependable, and cost-effective. It slower than original NTRU

Table 3. NTRU Previous work with variant and our analysis (*continue*)

N0. Ref	Algorithm	Principle	Finite field /deg	Public key	Attacks	Analysis
[12], [44], [2], [30], [31]	Q_TRU	NTRU Encrypt quaternion version is presented. QTRU's operation necessitates the use of a noncommutative quaternion algebra, $\mathbb{H} = \{a + ib + jc + kd \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}, i^2 = j^2 = k^2 = ijk = -1\}$.	$\frac{(-1, -1)}{\mathbb{Z}[X]/(X^N - 1)}$ Based on quaternion algebra	$H = H * P \text{ mod } q$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute force attack, • Lattice attack, • Message expansion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It has a very complicated and secure fundamental structure. • Hard to be attack by LLL
[45]	DB_TRU	NTRU designs Encrypt over a ring of binary truncated polynomials with positive integer coefficients that are dual special types, $R_N[x] = GF(2)[x]/(x^N - 1) \mid N \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. DBTRU outperforms NTRU Encrypt in terms of theoretical performance and security.	$\frac{GF(2)[x]}{x^N - 1} \mid N$	$h = g * F_1 * S \text{ mod } L$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meet-in-the-middle attacks • Multiple transmission attacks • Brute-force attacks. • Attack on f by using algebraic linear equations 	DBTRU equals NTRU in speed DBTRU's message-expansion factors are somewhat greater than NTRU's.
[11], [46], [47]	E_TRU	NTRU Encrypt is presented over the Eisenstein integer ring, $\mathbb{Z}[\omega] = \{a + b\omega \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Z}, i^2 = -1, \omega = e^{2i\pi/3}\}$	$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[\omega][X]}{X^N - 1}$ Ring of Eisenstein integers $\mathbb{Z}[W]$	$H = f * g \text{ mod } q$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute force attack, • Attack on the private key, • Meet in the middle attack, • Multiple transmission attack 	The security of NTRU, ETRU, and GNTRU in terms of decryption failure is very similar. However, in the most recent security releases.
[2], [38]	GR-NTRU	NTRU is derived Over a group ring, encrypt: $\mathbb{Z}[G] = \{\sum_{g \in G} a_g [g] \mid a_g \in \mathbb{Z} (\forall g \in G)\}$. GR-NTRU is less safe than NTRU Encrypt, according to the security comparison.	$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[G][X]}{X^N - 1}$	$h \equiv f'^{-1} g' \text{ MOD } q$ f successful keys are more than 1/1000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute force attack, • Attack on the private key, • Meet in the middle attack, • Multiple transmission attacks, Lattice attack 	Among these GR-NTRUs, the original NTRU and multivariate NTRU are the most secure. It is possible to expand the encryption to a functional level.
[48]	BI_TRU	Suggests NTRU Encrypt as an alternative to binary algebra, $BN_{\mathbb{R}} = \{a + bj \mid j^2 = 1, a, b \in \mathbb{R}\}$ BITRU is a multidimensional cryptosystem that can encrypt two independent communications from two different sources using two public keys, h and k. BITRU Encrypt has a higher level of security than NTRU Encrypt.	$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[X]}{X^N - 1}$	$h = \phi f_q \text{ mod } (q)$ $k = g_q w \text{ mod } (q)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attacking on private key 	BITRU has four times the security of NTRU due to the presence of two public keys h,k and four polynomial private keys.
[49]	CQ_TRU	NTRU Encrypt is presented over a commutative quaternion ring, $A = \{a + bi + cj + dk \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}, i^2 = a, j^2 = b, ij = k\}$. CQTRU is capable of encrypting and decrypting four messages concurrently and is immune to alternate key attacks, brute force attacks, and lattice attacks. CQTRU is a more secure encryption method than NTRU Encrypt.	$\frac{A[X]}{X^N - 1}$	$H = F_q \cdot G \text{ mod } q$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute Force Attacks • Lattice Attack 	-CQTRU allows for small polynomial dimensions while maintaining a high level of security. -CQTRU has four dimensions, so it can encrypt and decrypt four messages at same time

Table 3. NTRU Previous work with variant and our analysis (*continue*)

N0. Ref	Algorithm	Principle	Finite field /deg	Public key	Attacks	Analysis
[32]	HXD_TRU	NTRU is derived hexadecimally algebraically $\Psi = \{r_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{15} r_i x_i \mid r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{15} \in K\}$ where: $\frac{\mathbb{Z}[X]}{X^{N-1}}$ HXDTRU with an N-dimensional array is sixteen times faster than NTRU Encrypt with a 16-dimensional array.	$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[X]}{X^N - 1}$	$H = F_q \cdot G \in \Psi_q$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute Force Attack • Alternate Keys Attack • Lattice based Attacks 	The HXDTRU is a multidimensional cryptosystem capable of encrypting messages of length 16N in a single round (i.e. sixteen messages from a single source).
[42], [50], [30]	I_TRU	NTRU Encrypt is presented over the ring of integers modulo n denoted by $\mathbb{Z}=\mathbb{n}\mathbb{Z}$. As the comparison in the key generation, ITRU is only required $O(N^2)$ whereas NTRU Encrypt is required $O(N^2(\log^2 p + \log^2 q))$	$\frac{(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})[X]}{X^N - 1}$ Based on ideal lattices	$h = pg/f \in R_q^*$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute force attack, • Attack on the private key, • Meet in the middle attack, 	ITRU provides several advantages over NTRU, including a simpler parameter selection process, inevitability.
[51]	SQ_TRU	Presents NTRU Encrypt over coquaternions (also known as spit quaternion algebra), which is a new type of encryption over coquaternions. $H = \{q = q_0 + q_1i + q_2j + q_3k; q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3 \in R\}$ where T_y $R = \mathbb{Z}[x]/(x^N - 1)$.	$\frac{(-1, -1)}{\mathbb{Z}[x]/(x^N - 1)}$	$H = F \circ G_q(modq)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute Force Attack • Lattice based attacks 	The present lattice attack algorithms have a hard time attacking it.
[49], [52]	Pair_TRU	In this step, will create an NTRU Encrypt over the non-commutative matrix ring composed of $k \times k$ matrixes of polynomials for $\mathbb{Z}^* \mathbb{Z}$ and establish the NTRU Encrypt over it. In comparison to NTRU Encrypt, PairTRU is more resistant to linear algebra-based and lattice-based attacks.	$\frac{M(k, \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z})[x]}{(I_{k \times k}, I_{k \times k})x^N - (I_{k \times k}, I_{k \times k})}$	$h \equiv w * G_c(q, q) mod(\zeta)$ $H \equiv F_c(q, q) * cmod(q)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute Force Attack • Chosen Ciphertext Attacks • Message Expansion • Multiple Transmission Attack • Lattice Attack 	PairTRU, the cryptosystem is resistant to linear algebra and Lattice-based attacks. PairTRU is based on the NTRU core and use two-sided matrix multiplication.
[53]	D_NTRU	The definition of the truncated polynomial ring is introduced using the NTRU Encrypt as a point of reference. To complete its security proof of IND-CPA (Indistinguishability under Chosen Plaintext Attack), DNTRU additionally makes use of another cryptosystem, namely C-NTRU, as an aid.	$\frac{\mathbb{Z}[X]}{X^N - 1}$	$h_1 = (p \otimes f_{q_1}^{-1} \otimes g)_{q_1}$ $h_2 \leftarrow_R R_{q_2}$	Brute force attacks	The D-NTRU PKC algorithm uses a smaller ciphertext expansion than the original NTRU algorithm and is more efficient than NTRU.

Table 3. NTRU Previous work with variant and our analysis (*continue*)

No. Ref	Algorithm	Principle	Finite field /deg	Public key	Attacks	Analysis
[54], [52]	D_TRU1	Designs on the ring of dual integers (or the ring with no divisors) are shown. $\mathbb{D} = \mathbb{Z} + \epsilon\mathbb{Z}, \epsilon^2 = 0$ At	$\frac{\mathbb{D}[X]}{X^N - 1}$	$h = p$ t $(f_q * g)(modq)$	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brute force attacks • Meet-in-the-Middle attack • Lattice attacks 	Provides the same degree of security as NTRU while more secure than NTRU, it is also less efficient.

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